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Research Article

Homologous Series of Chemical Compounds in Three-component Systems ($A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-}$) and ($Zn^{2+} - Ge^{4+} - P^{3-}$) in Generalized Form

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Abstract

For the first time, a method for calculating formulas of homologous series of chemical compounds of the systems ($A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-}$) and ($Zn^{2+} - Ge^{4+} - P^{3-}$) in a generalized form is presented. The calculation is confirmed by the literature experimentally obtained compounds: thirteen compounds of the system ($Na^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-}$), seven – systems ($Li^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-}$), five – systems ($K^+ - V^{5+} - O^{2-}$), eight – systems ($Ba^{2+} - Cu^{2+} - O^{2-}$). Homological series in ($A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-}$) have the following generalized form: $A_{(t-kr+nr-r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t-kr+n)ab}$ and $A_{fbc} B_{(r-kt+nt-f)ac} C_{(r-kt+n)ab}$

In ($Zn^{2+} - Ge^{4+} - P^{3-}$) systems for the m -group the formulas of homologous series, that develops towards Ge_3P_4 , have the following generalized form: $Zn_r Ge_{(6r-6kt+6n-6t)P_{(8r-8kt+8n)}}$ and for αm -homologous series – $Zn_r Ge_{3n} P_{4(n+1)}$. A method for calculating formulas of homologous series of chemical compounds in a generalized form can be used for any system of chemical elements.

INTRODUCTION

The search for new Chemical Compounds (CC) in multicomponent systems of Chemical Elements (CE) is a difficult task. The great variety of properties of a set of Three-Component Chemical Compounds (TCC) is of great interest in solving a number of scientific and applied studies. There are known works in the literature that use the mathematical apparatus for predicting phases in multicomponent systems. Thus, semiempirical quantum-chemical methods, such as Hartree-Fock-Rutaan and Hartree-Fock-Slater methods [1-3], are used to calculate the formulae of hypothetical multicomponent CC. When using these methods to describe a chemical system, many physical and chemical phenomena must be taken into account. The exact solution of the basic laws leads to overcomplicated calculations. Therefore, for practically all CE systems, the solution of the corresponding electronic equations used in quantum-chemical calculations is only possible approximately. Well-known quantum-

chemical methods of calculation, allow to calculate the formula of any CC, are rather complicated and require special knowledge in the field of mathematical programming.

According to the works [4-7], knowledge of the laws of formation of Homological Series (HS) of chemical compounds can be included in the process of searching for new CC.

Thus, the author of the work [8, p. 190] believes that "...the activated complex theory consists in the fact that in the course of any chemical reaction, the initial configuration of atoms passes to the final one as a result of continuous change of interatomic distances", which is characterized by the formation of various critical intermediate configurations, i.e. activated complexes". On the basis of this idea, in the works [4-7] the method of calculation of formulae of HS of chemical compounds of three-component systems of CE ions was developed.

It is known [9,10] that multicomponent CE systems include CC, which are combined into different HS. As the HS develops, the fundamental properties of its members change in a regular way, which is determined by a regular change in the crystal structure of homologs [8-10]. In turn, the regular change in the crystal structure of homologs is determined by the regular change in their composition, which contributes to the search for new CC in [4-7]. In the works [9-11], the structural homology of inorganic CC of different systems of CE is discussed in detail.

So far, judging from the literature, the formulas of HS are known, which were obtained only empirically.

In the literature, there are known HS of systems with a single set of chemical elements:

$Ba_m Cu^{2+}_{m+n} O$ [12]; or $La_n Ni_n O_{3n-1}$ [13]; $La_{n+1} Ni_n O_{3n+1}$, $n = 1-5$ [14]; $La_{n+1} Ni_n O_{3n-1}$, $n = 7, 9, 13$ and 30 [15]; $La_{2n-4} Ni_2 O_{4n-5}$, $n = 5-8$ [16]; or $Fe^{2+n} Fe^{3+}_{2m} O_{n+3m}$ [17] or $Sr_{n+1} Ti_n O_{3n+1}$ [18]. Thus, in the $(Ba^{2+} - Cu^{2+} - O^{2-})$ system, the homologous series of CC is described by the formula $Ba_m Cu_{m+n} O_{3n-1}$, where $2m = 2n - 1$ [12], and in [17] it is reported that a series of CC belonging to the HS were obtained, described by the formula $nFeO \cdot mFe_2O_3 \equiv Fe^{2+}_n Fe^{3+}_{2m} O^{2-}_{n+3m}$.

Additionally, experimentally obtained inorganic CC described by formulas that exhibit regular changes in composition are known in the literature: $M_n O_{3n-1}$ ($M = Mo, W$) [19], $M_n O_{2n-1}$ ($M = Ti, V$) ($n = 4-10$) [20-24], $W_n O_{3n-2}$ ($n = 20, 38-40$) [24].

However, in the case of "Magnéli phases" in the systems $(M - O)$, where $M \equiv Mo, W, V, Ti$, [19-24] and in the system $(La - Ni - O)$ [13-16], all these formulas, without taking into account the existence of atom of metal with the same name with different atom valence in them, in our opinion, they cannot be considered correct. Following the electron neutrality of CC formulas, in all crystal lattices of CC belonging to the "Magnéli phases" described by formulas from [19-24], two metal ions of the same name with different atom valence should be present: for example, M^{5+} and M^{6+} in $Me_n O_{3n-1}$ or in $W_n O_{3n-2}$ ($M \equiv Mo, W$), or M^{3+} and M^{4+} in $M_n O_{2n-1}$ ($M \equiv Ti, V$). In the formulas described in [13-16] two ions Ni^{2+} and Ni^{3+} with different atom valence should be present as equal chemical entities, determining the existence of the crystal lattice of CC. That is why the formulas of "Magnéli phases" from [19-24], in our opinion, should be attributed not to two-component, but to three-component CE systems. In turn, the formulas related to the $(La - Ni - O)$ system [16-19] belong not to a three-component system but to a four-component CE system, $(La^{3+} - Ni^{2+} - Ni^{3+})$. For this reason, the formulas from [19-24], in our opinion, could be written as follows:

$Me_n O_{3n-1} \equiv Me^{5+}_2 Me^{6+}_{n-2} O_{3n-1}$, where ($Me \equiv Mo, W$) and $n = 8-12, 14$ [19]; or $Me_n O_{2n-1} \equiv Me^{3+}_2 Me^{4+}_{n-2} O_{2n-1}$, where ($Me \equiv Ti, V$) and $n = 4-10$ [20-24]; or $W_n O_{3n-2} \equiv W^{5+}_4 W^{6+}_{n-4} O_{3n-2}$, where $n = 20, 38-40$ [24], and the formulas from [13-16] are suggested to be written as follows: $La_n Ni_n O_{3n-1}$ [13] $\equiv La_n Ni^{2+}_2 Ni^{3+}_{n-2} O_{3n-1}$, $La_{n+1} Ni_n O_{3n+1}$ [14] $\equiv La_{n+1} Ni^{2+} Ni^{3+}_{n-1} O_{3n+1}$, $La_{n+1} Ni_n O_{3n-1}$ [15] $\equiv La_{n+1} Ni^{2+} Ni^{3+}_{n-1} O_{3n-1}$ and $La_{2n-4} Ni_n O_{4n-5}$ [16] $\equiv La_{2n-4} Ni^{2+}_{n-2} Ni^{3+}_2 O_{4n-5}$.

In the literature, for the system $(M^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$, where $M^+ \equiv Li^+, Na^+, K^+, Rb^+, Cs^+$, a series of formulas for experimentally obtained TCC is known, generalized for $n = 1-9$ in the form of $M^+ Ti^{4+}_4 O_{2(n+1)}$ [24].

The aim of this study is to develop a method for calculating the formulas of a homologous series of three-component systems of chemical elements in a generalized form using the geometric features of the triangle representing the system of chemical element ions.

Justification of the method for calculating homologous series of chemical compounds

The method for calculating HS of three-component systems developed in [4-7] allows, in our opinion, for the generalized determination of HS formulas. This conclusion is drawn from the findings presented in [6,7], which provide numerous confirmations of the accuracy of the HS calculation method for a range of three-component systems through experimental results taken from the literature. It should be noted, however, that the laws governing the formation of individual CC and the laws governing the formation of HS are different. Before the publications of [4-7], there was no possibility in the literature to predict the formation scheme of HS. In some cases, HS formulas were only experimentally determined in works [13-24].

Based on the works [4-7], the justification for the generalized method of calculating HS can be formulated as follows:

1) In our view, the rule (or scheme) for forming HS of chemical compounds can be formulated by considering all possible directions of chemical interactions between the components of the system, as allowed by the combination of the valence electron count of chemical elements and the composition of complex atomic clusters in the system. In reality, only ions of elementary substances and "certain intermediate atom configurations critical for a given reaction" participate in chemical interactions [8]. In our case, these are activated CC and charge clusters (ChCl). It is clear that determining the formula of HS is possible if, among the many presumed directions of chemical interaction between the components of the CE system, we can select those responsible for the formation of HS. Therefore, to

solve this problem, the CE system must be represented as ions, as only ions can chemically interact with each other, producing intermediate, more complex, compositionally charged clusters and activated multi-component CC. To do this, the system is represented as a triangle (Figures 1-3), with CE ions placed at its vertices.

2) It was found that the geometric features of the triangle representing the system of CE ions consist of representing the reaction of the interaction between any pair of reacting system components as a line segment, where each pair of reactants and the product of their interaction lie on a line segment unique to them. In cases where line segments connecting different pairs of chemically interacting system components intersect at a single point, the common product of the interaction, ChCl or activated CC, must be located at that point. This feature is explained by the difference in the laws governing the interaction of different pairs of reactants, which are determined by the different combinations of valence ions of CE and the composition of interacting pairs of reactants represented by different line segments: at the point of intersection of these line segments, different laws of chemical interaction of different pairs of chemical entities cannot coexist simultaneously.

Thus, the calculation of HS formulas, i.e., the search for new HS homologs, is based on the premise that homologs are located within a triangle at the intersection of line segments connecting different pairs of chemically interacting components of the system, including ions, CC and ChCl.

3) Next, we will consider that homologs enriched with the two-component CC (TwCC), $A_c C_a$, belong to the p -groups of HS, while homologs enriched with the $B_c C_b$ cluster belong to the m -groups of HS – Figure 1-3. HS are formed depending on the direction of development through a chain of sequentially occurring interactions of TCC with cation A^{a+} – the development direction of p -groups of HS is $A_c C_a$. When TCC interacts with cation B^{b+} – the m -groups of HS develop towards $B_c C_b$.

The formation of HS involves three-component charge clusters (TChCl_n) through interaction with anion C^{c-} (Figures 1-3).

The formation of HS is described by the following scheme:

In the text, the determined formulas of CC and ChCl as reactants and products of their interaction are highlighted

in bold. The value of n is determined experimentally, where n represents the position of the homolog in HS, ($1 \leq n$).

4) Activated TXC_n are located on line segments ($A_c C_a - B_c C_b$) – Figures 1-3. In works [4-6], the nature of the connection of the same TCC_n , which simultaneously belongs to both the p -groups and m -groups of HS, is described. Following the conditions outlined in paragraph 3 regarding the membership of TCC in p -groups and m -groups of HS, it can be concluded that in the case of p -groups of HS, its first homologs, $TCC_{n=1}$, are located on the line segment ($p. 2 - B_c C_b$), excluding $B_c C_b$, and the clusters $TCC_{n>1}$ are located on the line segment ($p. 2 - A_c C_a$), excluding point 2 and $A_c C_a$ (Figures 1,2).

In the case where the same TCC_n cluster belongs to the m -group of HS, its first homologs, $TCC_{n=1}$, are located on the line segment ($p. 2 - A_c C_a$), excluding $A_c C_a$. The clusters $TCC_{n>1}$ are located on the line segment ($p. 2 - B_c C_b$), excluding $p. 2$ and $B_c C_b$ (Figures 1,3).

5) Clusters $TChCl_{n=1}$, belonging to p -groups of HS, are located on the line segment ($p. 1 - B^{b+}$), excluding B^{b+} , and clusters $TChCl_{n>1}$ are located on the line segment ($p. 1 - A_c C_a$), excluding $p. 1$ and $A_c C_a$ – Figures 1,2. In the text and in Figure 1, the following notations are used: $p. 1 \equiv$ point 1, $p. 2 \equiv$ point 2, $p. 3 \equiv$ point 3, and so on.

In the case where the $TChCl_n$ cluster belongs to the m -group of HS, its first homologs, $TChCl_{n=1}$, are located on the line segment ($p. 1 - A^{a+}$), excluding A^{a+} , and clusters $TChCl_{n>1}$ are located on the line segment ($p. 1 - B_c C_b$), excluding $p. 1$ and $B_c C_b$ (Figures 1,3).

6) TCC_n and $TChCl_n$, occupying the same position in the same HS, are linked by the reaction: $TChCl_n + C^{c-} \rightarrow TCC_n, \dots \dots \dots (2)$

7) Any known TCC is necessarily a member of some HS.

8) Any HS consists of a CC branch and a ChCl branch, the members of which are linked by reaction (2). Each branch of the same HS develops towards enrichment with only one Two-component CC (TwCC), either $A_c C_a$ or $B_c C_b$.

9) The geometric features of the triangle, if following scheme (1), ensure a systematic and periodic change in the composition of homologs in HS.

10) The difference in compositions, Δ , of any adjacent homologs in the same HS is constant: $\Delta_{m(p)} = TCC_{n+1} - TCC_n = TChCl_{n+1} - TChCl_n, \dots \dots \dots (3)$

11) The charges of all ChCl in the same HS are identical.

12) In the case of determining the formulas of HS to which some known (basic) $TCC_{n(bas)}$ belongs, the calculation of HS formulas is carried out as follows: first, the formulas of $TChCl_{n(bas)}$, $TCC_{n(bas)+1}$, and $TChCl_{n(bas)+1}$ are calculated, then the formulas of Δ and the first terms, $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TChCl_{n=1}$, of the considered HS are determined. Formulas $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TChCl_{n=1}$ are calculated by subtracting the maximum number of times the formula $\Delta_{m(p)}$ from the formulas of basic clusters while retaining the minimum number of the cation contained in the formula $\Delta_{m(p)}$ in their composition:

$$TCC_{n(bas)} - k \cdot \Delta_{m(p)} = TCC_{n=1} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

$$TChCl_{n(bas)} - k \cdot \Delta_{m(p)} = TChCl_{n=1} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

where $(0 \leq k)$. If $k = 0$, then $n(bas) = 1$.

13) The formula of any homolog in the same HS, i.e., the formula of the HS, is determined as follows:

$$CC \text{ branch: } TCC_{n=1} + (n-1) \cdot \Delta_{m(p)} = TCC_n \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

$$ChCl \text{ branch: } TChCl_{n=1} + (n-1) \cdot \Delta_{m(p)} = TChCl_n \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

14) When calculating HS, it should be taken into account that one of the CE may have different valencies, being not only a component that does not introduce impurities into the crystalline lattice of TCC but also one of the main CE in the crystalline lattice.

In practice, researchers often need to determine the formulas of HS to which a known $TCC_{n(bas)}$ already belongs. In the formation of these HS, any TCC_n can participate, including $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TCC_{n>1}$.

Calculation of homologous series in the $(A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-})$ system

Let's examine the sequentially occurring chemical reactions in a three-component system. The formation of HS occurs according to scheme (1). The system $(A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-})$ is initially in a state where the interaction of a positively charged ion with an anion will lead to the formation of activated TwCC, $A_c C_a$ and $B_c C_b$ (Figure 1).

$$cA^{a+} + aC^{c-} = A_c C_a \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

$$cB^{b+} + bC^{c-} = B_c C_b \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Activated TwCC, $A_c C_a$ and $B_c C_b$ can interact with each other to form TCC_n based on the ratios of ions A^{a+} , B^{b+} and C^{c-} in TCC_n based on the ratios of ions A^{a+} , B^{b+} and C^{c-} in $TChCl_n$, which participate in reaction (2):

$$x \cdot A_c C_a + y \cdot B_c C_b = (A_{xc} B_{yc} C_{(x+y)ab}) = TCC_n \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

Furthermore, according to the initial ratios of ions in

TCC_n and $TChCl_n$, the interaction of positively charged ions with each other leads to the formation of two-component charged clusters ($TwChCl_n$), which are connected to TCC_n and $TChCl_n$ by reaction (2), where $(1 \leq n)$:

$$x \cdot A^{a+} + y \cdot B^{b+} = ([A_{xb} B_{ya}]^{(x+y)ab+} = TwChCl_n) \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

The combined interaction of $(TChCl_{n=1} = p.1)$ and $TwChCl_{n=1}$ with anion C^{c-} according to (2), as well as activated $A_c C_a$ and $B_c C_b$ with each other leads to the formation of a cluster of $(TCC_{n=1} = p.1)$ – Figure 1. Thus, the clusters $(TChCl_{n=1} = p.1)$, $(TwChCl_{n=1} = p.3)$ and $(TCC_{n=1} = p.2)$ turn out to be the founders of two groups of HS, *am*-group and *ap*-group, since $(TChCl_{n=1} = p.1)$ and $(TCC_{n=1} = p.2)$ can interact with both B^{b+} and A^{a+} , respectively. The interactions mentioned are characterized by the intersection of segments corresponding to the reacting components of the CE system. Thus, the formation of different clusters $TChCl_n$ are characterized by the intersection of segments $(A_c C_a - B^{b+})$ and $(B_c C_b - A^{a+})$, and the formation of cluster TCC_n is characterized by the intersection of segments $(TChCl_n - C^{c-})$, $(A^{a+} - B^{b+})$ and $(A_c C_a - B_c C_b)$, which is described by the following reaction equations in the formation of the *am*-group of HS and *ap*-group of HS (Figure 1).

$$bA_c C_a + acB^{b+} = aB_c C_b + bA^{a+} = ([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p.1) \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

$$([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p.1) + abC^{c-} = \{bA^{a+} + acB^{b+} = ([A_{bc} B_{ac}]^{2abc+} = TwChCl_{n=1} = p.3) + 2abC^{c-} = bA_c C_a + aB_c C_b = (A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}) = TCC_{n=1} = p.2) \dots \dots \dots (13)$$

Figure 1: System $(A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-})$: *ap*-HS ($A_c C_a$ direction) and *am*-HS ($B_c C_b$ direction).
ap-HS: (p. 1 = $TChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+}$), (p. 2 = $TCC_{n(bas)=1} = A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}$) (p. 3 = $TwChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{bc} B_{ac}]^{2abc+}$), (p. 4 = $TChCl_{n=2} = [A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+}$), (p. 5 = $TCC_{n=2} = A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{3ab}$), (p. 6 = $TwChCl_{n=2} = [A_{bc} B_{2ac}]^{3abc+}$);
am-HS: (p. 1 = $TChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{bc} B_{ac}]^{abc+}$), (p. 2 = $TCC_{n(bas)=1} = A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}$), (p. 3 = $TwChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{bc} B_{ac}]^{2abc+}$), (p. 7 = $TChCl_{n=2} = [A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+}$), (p. 8 = $TCC_{n=2} = A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{3ab}$), (p. 9 = $TwChCl_{n=2} = [A_{bc} B_{2ac}]^{3abc+}$).

Calculation of the formula for *ap*-HS developing

towards $A_c C_a$: The continuous nature of the chemical interaction of the components of the system ($A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^c$) and the formation of HS implies that the formation of *p*-groups of HS is described by the interaction of TCC_n with A^{a+} . The interaction of $TChCl_n$ and $TwChCl_n$ with C^c is characterized by the intersection of segments ($TCC_n - A^{a+}$) and ($B^{b+} - A_c C_a$) at the point corresponding to $TChCl_{n+1}$, including the intersection of segments ($TCC_{n+1} - C^c$) and ($TwChCl_n - C^c$) with the segment ($A_c C_a - B_c C_b$) at the point corresponding to TCC_{n+1} – Figure 1. In turn, clusters ($A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2$) interact with A^{a+} , and activated $A_c C_a$ reacting with B^{b+} to form ($TChCl_{n=2} = p. 4$), and clusters ($TwChCl_{n+1} = p. 6$) and ($TChCl_{n+1} = p. 4$) interact with C^c and form ($TCC_{n+1} = p. 5$) – Figure 1. These interactions begin to form *ap*-HS, the members of which, as this HS develops, are enriched with the $A_c C_a$ component, which for *ap*-HS is described by the reaction equation (Figure 1).

$$(A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) + bcA^{a+} = acB^{b+} + 2bA_c C_a = ([A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 4) \dots (14)$$

$$([A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 4) + abC^c = \{2bcA^{a+} + acB^{b+} = ([A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}]^{3abc+} = TwChCl_{n=2} = p. 6)\} = 2bA_c C_a + aB_c C_b = aB_c C_b = (A_{2bc} B_{2ac} C_{3ab} = TCC_{n=2} = p. 5) \dots (15)$$

According to (3), (6) and (7) the formula Δ_{ap} is determined as follows:

$$\Delta_{ap} = (A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{3ab} = TCC_{n=2} = p. 5) - (A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) = [A_{2bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 4) - ([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p. 1) = A_{bc} C_{ab} \dots (16)$$

Knowledge of the formulas of the first homologs ($TCC_{n=1} = p. 2$), ($TChCl_{n=1} = p. 1$), and Δ_{ap} allows us to determine the formulas of both branches of *ap*-HS:

$$\text{CC branch in } ap\text{-HS: } (A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) + (n-1) A_{bc} C_{ab} = A_{nbc} B_{nac} C_{(n+1)ab} \dots (17)$$

$$\text{ChCl branch in } ap\text{-HS: } ([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p. 1) + (n-1) A_{bc} C_{ab} = [A_{nbc} B_{nac} C_{nab}]^{abc+} \dots (18)$$

The formulas for both branches of HS in other *p*-group HS are determined in accordance with dependencies (4)-(7).

Calculation of the formula for *am*-HS developing

towards $B_c C_b$: In the case where the cluster ($TCC_{n=1} = p. 2$) reacts with cation B^{b+} to form ($TChCl_{n=2} = p. 7$), and cluster ($TChCl_{n=2} = p. 7$) reacts with anion C^c , and to form ($TCC_{n=2} = p. 8$) but they participate in the formation of the *am*-group of HS (Figure 1).

$$(A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) + acB^{b+} = bcA^{a+} + 2aB_c C_b = ([A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 7) \dots (19)$$

$$([A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 7) + abC^c = \{2bcA^{a+} +$$

$$acB^{b+} = ([A_{bc} B_{2ac}]^{3abc+} = TwChCl_{n=2} = p. 9) + 2abC^c = bA_c C_a + 2aB_c C_b = aB_c C_b = (A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{3ab} = TCC_{n=2} = p. 8) \dots (20)$$

According to (3), (6), and (7) the formula Δ_{am} , TCC_n , and $TChCl_n$ are determined by the formulas of both branches of *am*-HS:

$$\Delta_{am} = (A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{3ab} = TCC_{n=2} = p. 5) - (A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) = [A_{bc} B_{2ac} C_{2ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=2} = p. 4) - ([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p. 1) = B_{ac} C_{ab} \dots (21)$$

$$\text{CC branch in } am\text{-HS: } (A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = TCC_{n=1} = p. 2) + (n-1) B_{ac} C_{ab} = A_{bc} B_{nac} C_{(n+1)ab} \dots (22)$$

$$\text{ChCl branch in } am\text{-HS: } ([A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{ab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n=1} = p. 1) + (n-1) B_{ac} C_{ab} = [A_{bc} B_{nac} C_{nab}]^{abc+} \dots (23)$$

The formulas for both branches of HS in other *m*-group HS are determined in accordance with dependencies (4)-(7).

Calculation of the generalized formula for homologous series to which a known (Basic) $TCC_{n(bas)}$ belong:

In the process of designing various devices, researchers often face the task of determining the formulas of TCC that would possess more suitable properties compared to the currently used TCC in the device. In situations where the composition of the utilized TCC is known and experimentally confirmed, we will consider this cluster as the basic one $TCC_{n(bas)}$. The problem of finding new $TCC_{n \neq n(bas)}$ can be solved by identifying the formulas of HS to which the basic $TCC_{n(bas)}$ belongs. In the desired HS, the fundamental properties of homologs, including $TCC_{n(bas)}$, change periodically and systematically [8,9]. To determine the regularity of HS formation in a generalized form, it is necessary to represent the formula of $TCC_{n(bas)}$ appropriately. Thus, the formula of any TCC, including $TCC_{n(bas)}$, can be expressed in a generalized form as follows:

$$tA_c C_a + rB_c C_b = A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} \dots (24)$$

Where ($0 < t, r$).

Calculation of the generalized formula for the *p*-Group of ΓC to which a known (Basic) ($TCC_{n(bas)}$ = $A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}$) belongs:

In accordance with paragraphs 3-5, the basic cluster, represented in a generalized form as ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)}$), begins to form the *p*-group of HS by interacting with A^{a+} . In this case, the formulas of $TChCl_{n(bas)}$ and $TwChCl_{n(bas)}$, associated with $TCC_{n(bas)}$ by reaction (2), are determined by the intersection of segments $\{(A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10) - p. 12) - A^{a+}\}$, and $\{(TwChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 12) - C^c\}$ and ($B^{b+} - A_c C_a$), which is described by the reaction equation (Figure 2).

$$\{racB^{b+} + tbA_c C_a = ([A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{abc+} = TChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 11)\} +$$

Figure 2: System ($A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-}$): p -group HS ($A_c C_a$ direction).
 (p. 10 = $TCC_{n(bas)=1} = A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}$), (p. 11 = $TChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c}$), (p. 12 = $TwChCl_{n(bas)=1} = [A_{tbc} B_{rac}]^{(t+r)abc+}$), (p. 13 = $TChCl_{n(bas)=2} = [A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{rab+c}$), (p. 14 = $TCC_{n=2} = A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+2r)ab}$), (p. 15 = $TwChCl_{n=2} = [A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac}]^{(t+2r)abc+}$), (p. 16 = $TChCl_{n=3} = A_{(t+2r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+2r)ab}$), (p. 17 = $TCC_{n=3} = A_{(t+2r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+3r)ab}$), (p. 18 = $TwChCl_{n=3} = [A_{(t+2r)bc} B_{rac}]^{(t+3r)abc+}$).

$$rabC^{c-} = \{tbcA^{a+} + racB^{b+} = ([A_{tbc} B_{rac}]^{(t+r)abc+} = TwChCl_{n(bas)}) = p. 12\} + (t+r)abC^{c-} = (A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10).....(25)$$

The initiation of the formation of the p -group of HS based on ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10$) is characterized by the intersection of segments ($TCC_{n(bas)} - A^{a+}$), and ($B^{b+} - A_c C_a$) at a point corresponding to ($TChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 13$), as well as the intersection of segments $\{(TChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 13) - C^{c-}\}$ and $\{(TwChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 12) - C^{c-}\}$ with the segment ($A_c C_a - B_c C_b$) at a point corresponding to ($TCC_{n(bas)+1} = p. 14$), which is described by the reaction equations (Figure 2).

$$(A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)=1} = p. 10) + rbcA^{a+} = racB^{b+} + (t+r) bA_c C_a = ([A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 13).....(26)$$

$$([A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 13) + rabC^{c-} = (t+r)bA_c C_a + raB_c C_b = \{(t+r)bcA^{a+} + racB^{b+} = (TwChCl_{n(bas)+1} = [A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac}]^{(t+2r)abc+} = p. 15)\} + (t+2r)abC^{c-} = (A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+2r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)+1} = p. 14).....(27)$$

The formula Δ_p , $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TChCl_{n=1}$ for the p -group of HS is determined according to (3)-(5), (25)-(27):
 $\Delta_p = (A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+2r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)+1} = p. 14) - (A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10) = ([A_{(t+r)bc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)+1} = p. 13) - ([A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 11) = A_{tbc} C_{rab}(28)$
 $TCC_{n=1} = (A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10) - k \cdot A_{tbc} C_{rab} = A_{(t-k)rbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r-k)rab}(29)$
 $TChCl_{n=1} = ([A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 11) - k \cdot A_{tbc} C_{rab} = [A_{(t-k)rbc} B_{rac} C_{(t-k)rab}]^{rab+c}(30)$

Where ($0 \leq k$) and k characterizes the positioning of

$TCC_{n(bas)}$ in HS, and for ap -HS corresponds $n(bas) = 1$ and $k = 0$.

As can be seen, the determination of the composition of the first homologs and the formulas of both branches of the sought p -group of HS according to the formulas (29), (30), (6), and (7) depends on the relationship between the values t and $k \cdot r$. In this case, two variants are possible:

1) Inequality ($t \leq k \cdot r$) when ($t, r, k > 0$) does not allow obtaining formulas for $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TChCl_{n=1}$ according to (29) and (30) by subtracting the product ($k \cdot \Delta_p \equiv k \cdot A_{tbc} C_{rab}$) from the formulas ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10$) and ($[A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 11$). It follows that ($k = 0$) and $n(bas) = 1$. This fast indicates that when ($t \leq k \cdot r$), the basic cluster is the first homolog ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)=1} = p. 10$) in this p -group of HS. Therefore, any homologue or both branches of the desired p -group of HS is determined according to (6), (7), and (28):

$$CC \text{ branch in } p\text{-group of HS} - (A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)=1} = p. 10) + (n-1)A_{tbc} C_{rab} = A_{\{t+r(n-1)\}bc} B_{rac} C_{\{t+rn\}ab}(31)$$

$$ChCl \text{ branch in } p\text{-group of HS} - ([A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)=1} = p. 11) + (n-1)A_{tbc} C_{rab} = [A_{\{t+r(n-1)\}bc} B_{rac} C_{\{t+rn\}ab}]^{rab+c}(32)$$

2) In the case when the inequality ($k \cdot r < t$) holds, to determine the composition of the first homologs, it is possible to subtract the product ($k \cdot \Delta_p \equiv k \cdot A_{tbc} C_{rab}$) from the formulas of the basic clusters ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10$) and ($[A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{tab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n(bas)} = p. 11$), i.e. at ($0 < k$) and $\{n(bas) > 1\}$. Then the first members of $TCC_{n=1}$ and $TChCl_{n=1}$ of the sought p -group of HS will be determined by expressions (29) and (30). Any homologue or both branches of the p -group of HS will be determined according to (6), (7), (28), (29), and (30):

$$CC \text{ branch in } p\text{-group of HS} - (A_{(t-k)rbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r-k)rab} = TCC_{n=1}) + (n-1)A_{tbc} C_{rab} = A_{\{t-kr+(n-1)r\}bc} B_{rac} C_{\{t-kr+n\}ab}(33)$$

$$ChCl \text{ branch in } p\text{-group of HS} - ([A_{(t-k)rbc} B_{rac} C_{(t-k)rab}]^{rab+c} = TChCl_{n=1}) + (n-1)A_{tbc} C_{rab} = [A_{\{t-kr+(n-1)r\}bc} B_{rac} C_{\{t-kr+(n-1)r\}ab}]^{rab+c}(34)$$

It should be noted that for the p -group of HS in both cases ($t \leq k \cdot r$) and ($kr < t$) cluster $TCC_{n=1}$ is located in the p. 2, and cluster $TCC_{n(bas) > 1}$ should be on the segment ($p. 2 - A_c C_a$) excluding p. 2 and $A_c C_a$. Cluster $TChCl_{n=1}$ is located in the on the segment ($p. 1 - B^{b+}$) excluding p. 1 and cluster $TCC_{n(bas) > 1}$ should be on the segment ($p. 1 - A_c C_a$) excluding p. 1 and $A_c C_a$ (Figure 2).

Comparing the concentration coefficients for A^{a+} in the formula of the base cluster ($A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 10$) and in the formula of the homologue in the p -group HS in

the generalized form $A_{t-k-r+\{n(\text{bas})-1\}r} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\{t-k-r+n(\text{bas})-r\}ab}$ from (33), it can be seen that there is equality $\{rn(\text{bas}) - r - k \cdot r\} = 0$ holds. Then for $(r \neq 0)$ we get:

$$k = \{n(\text{bas}) - 1\} \dots \dots \dots (35)$$

In reality, the value of k is determined during the calculation of the p -group HS in accordance with the possibility of subtracting the product $(k \cdot \Delta_p \equiv k \cdot A_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}})$ from the formula $\{A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}\}$: $k \cdot r$ and t are compared. The values of t and r are determined by the formula $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}$. By setting the value of n , it is possible, in accordance with the formulas $(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 10)$, (33) and (35), to calculate the formula of any homologue of TCC_n belonging to the p -group of HS.

Calculation of the generalized formula for the m -group of hs to which the known (basic) $(\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab})$ belongs: Let the cluster $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}$, the formula of which is represented in a generalized form as $(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19)$, interact with B^{b+} to start forming the HS, which in this case will belong to the m -group of HS. In this process, the formulas for $(\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 20)$ and $(\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 21)$ related to $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}$ by reaction (2) are determined by the composition of $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}$, which is described by the reaction equation:

$$\{tbcA^{a+} + racB^{b+} = ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}}]^{(t+r)abc+} = \text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 21)\} + (t+r)abC^{c-} = \{tbcA^{a+} + raB_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}} = ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 20) + tabC^{c-} = (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19) \dots \dots (36)$$

The formation of the m -group of HS based on $(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19)$ is characterized by the intersection of the segments $(\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} - B^{b+})$ and $(A^{a+} - B_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}})$ at the point corresponding to $(\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 22)$, as well as the intersection of the segments $\{(\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 22) - C^{c-}\}$ and $\{(\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 24) - C^{c-}\}$ with the segment $(A_{\text{c}} C_{\text{a}} - B_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}})$ at the point corresponding to $(\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 23)$ – Figure 3, which is described by the following reaction equations:

$$(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 19) + tacB^{b+} = tbcA^{a+} + (t+r)abB_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}} = ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 22) \dots \dots \dots (37)$$

$$([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 22) + tabC^{c-} = tbA_{\text{c}} C_{\text{a}} + (t+r)abB_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}} = \{tbcA^{a+} + (t+r)abB^{b+} = (\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 24)\} + (t+r)abC^{c-} = (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 23) \dots \dots \dots (38)$$

The formula Δ_m , TCC_{n-1} , and TChCl_{n-1} are determined according to (3), (4), (5), (36)-(38):

$$\Delta_m = (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1}) - (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})}) = ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = \text{TChCl}_{n-1})$$

Figure 3: System $(A^{a+} - B^{b+} - C^{c-})$: m -group HS $(B_{\text{c}} C_{\text{b}}$ direction).
 (p. 19 = $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab}$), (p. 20 = $\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+}$), (p. 21 = $\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}}]^{(t+r)abc+}$), (p. 22 = $\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+2} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab}]^{tabc+}$), (p. 23 = $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+2} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(2t+r)ab}$), (p. 24 = $\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+2} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}}]^{(2t+r)abc+}$), (p. 25 = $\text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+3} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(2t+r)ab}]^{tabc+}$), (p. 26 = $\text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+3} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(3t+r)ab}$), (p. 27 = $\text{TwChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+3} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}}]^{(3t+r)abc+}$).

$$) - ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})}) = B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{t}} \dots \dots \dots (39)$$

$$\text{TCC}_{n-1} = (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19) - k \cdot B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(r-k)t} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} \dots \dots \dots (40)$$

$$\text{TChCl}_{n-1} = ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 20) - k \cdot B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(r-k)t} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} \dots \dots \dots (41)$$

As can be seen from equations (40) and (41), determining the composition of the first homologs and formulas of both branches of the sought m -group of HS depends on the relationship between the values of r and $k \cdot t$. In this regard, two variants are possible:

1) In the case of the inequality $(r \leq k \cdot t)$ with $\{0 < t, r, k\}$, it is not possible to obtain the compositions of TCC_{n-1} and TChCl_{n-1} according to (4) and (5) by subtracting the formula $(\Delta_m = B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}})$ from the formulas $(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19)$ and $([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 20)$. In this scenario, it implies that $(k = 0)$, and $\{n(\text{bas}) = 1\}$. Consequently, both branches of the m -group of HS can be determined according to (6), (7), and (39)-(41):

$$\text{CC branch of } m\text{-group of HS} - (A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 19) + (n-1)B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}} = A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\{r+t(n-1)\}ab} \dots \dots \dots (42)$$

$$\text{ChCl branch of } m\text{-group of HS} - ([A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\text{rab}}]^{tabc+} = \text{TChCl}_{n(\text{bas})+1} = p. 20) + (n-1)B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}} = [A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{\{r+t(n-1)\}ab}]^{tabc+} \dots \dots \dots (43)$$

2) In the case of the inequality $(k \cdot t < r)$, to determine the formulas of the first homologs, it is possible to subtract the product $(k \cdot \Delta_m \equiv k \cdot B_{\text{tac}} C_{\text{tab}})$ from the composition of the basic clusters $(A_{\text{tbc}} B_{\text{rac}} C_{(t+r)ab} = \text{TCC}_{n(\text{bas})} = p. 19)$ and

$([A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{rab}]^{tabc+} = TChCl_{n(bas)=1} = p. 20)$, i.e., $(0 < k)$. In this scenario, the first members of the sought m -group of HS will be determined by equations (37) and (38). Both branches of the m -group of HS will be determined according to (6), (7), (36), (37), and (38):

$$CC \text{ branch of } m\text{-group of HS} - A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n=1} + (n-1)B_{tac} C_{tab} = A_{tbc} B_{\{r-kt+(n-1)t\}ac} C_{\{r-k-t+nt\}ab} \dots (44)$$

$$ChCl \text{ branch of } m\text{-group of HS} - ([A_{tbc} B_{(r-k)t} C_{(r-k)t}])^{tabc+} = TChCl_{n=1} + (n-1)B_{tac} C_{tab} = [A_{tbc} B_{\{r-k-t+(n-1)t\}ac} C_{\{r-k-t+(n-1)t\}ab}]^{tabc+} \dots (45)$$

It should be noted that for the m -group of HS in both cases $(r \leq k \cdot t)$ and $(k \cdot t < r)$ cluster $TCC_{n=1}$ is located in the p. 2, and cluster $TCC_{n(bas) > 1}$ should be on the segment $(p. 2 - B_c C_b)$ excluding p. 2 and $B_c C_b$. Cluster $TChCl_{n=1}$ is located in the on the segment $(p. 1 - A^{+})$ excluding p. 1 and cluster $TCC_{n(bas) > 1}$ should be on the segment $(p. 1 - B_c C_b)$ excluding p. 1 and $B_c C_b$ (Figure 3).

Comparing the concentration coefficients for B^{b+} in the formula of the base cluster $(A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 19)$ and in the formula of the homologue in the m -group HS in the generalized form $A_{tbc} B_{\{r-kt+(n-1)t\}ac} C_{\{r-k-t+nt\}ab}$ from (44), it can be seen that there is equality $\{t \cdot n(bas) - t - k \cdot t = 0\}$ holds. Then for $(t \neq 0)$ we get:

$$\{k = \{n(bas) - 1\} \dots (46)$$

In reality, the value of k is determined during the calculation of the m -group HS in accordance with the possibility of subtracting the product $(k \cdot \Delta_m \equiv k \cdot A_{tbc} C_{rab})$ from the formula $\{A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)}\}$: $k \cdot t$ and r are compared. The values of t and r are determined by the formula $TCC_{n(bas)}$. By setting the value of n , it is possible, in accordance with the formulas $(A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} = TCC_{n(bas)} = p. 19)$, (44), and (45), to calculate the formula of any homologue of TCC_n belonging to the m -group of HS.

Calculation of the generalized formula for the m -group of HS developing towards Ge_3P_4 in the system $(Zn^{2+} - Ge^{4+} - P^{3-})$ to which the known (basic) $(TCC_{n(bas)} = ZnGeP_2)$ belongs:

As an example of the practical application of the above HS formulas in a generalized form, we calculate the formula of the m -group of HS, which belongs to the well-known (basic) $(TCC_{n(bas)} = ZnGeP_2 \equiv A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab})$. Attention to the system $(Zn^{2+} - Ge^{4+} - P^{3-})$ and, in particular, to $ZnGeP_2$ is caused by the fact that the $ZnGeP_2$ compound, having a chalcopyrite crystal structure, has highly effective nonlinear optical characteristics that are used for parametric conversion of medium and far infrared radiation range, as well as for terahertz radiation [25]. The calculated HS formula based on $(TCC_{n(bas)} = ZnGeP_2)$ will allow us to determine the

formulas of other unknown TCC-homologues that may be potential substitutes for the compound $ZnGeP_2$.

When solving this problem, we agree that homologues, as they develop m -HS, enriched by a cluster $(Ge_3P_4 \equiv B_c C_b)$.

So, for $(TCC_{n(bas)} = ZnGeP_2 \equiv A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab})$ we get: $A^{a+} \equiv Zn^{2+}$, $B^{b+} \equiv Ge^{4+}$, $C^{c-} \equiv P^{3-}$, $bc = 12$, $ac = 6$, $ab = 8$, $abc = 24$, $tbc = 1$, $t = 1/12$, $rac = 1$, $r = 1/6$, $(t+r)ab = 2$, $(t+r) = 2/8$. Then the following is true:

$$(TCC_{n(bas)} = A_{tbc} B_{rac} C_{(t+r)ab} \equiv ZnGeP_2 \equiv Zn_{12/12} Ge_{6/6} P_{16/8}) \dots (47)$$

In order to determine the position of the base cluster in the HS m -group, it is necessary to determine the formula Δ_m (direction Ge_3P_4) in accordance with (39):

$$\Delta_m = B_{tac} C_{tab} = Ge_{6t} P_{8t} \equiv Ge_{6/12} P_{8/12} \dots (48)$$

To determine the value of k , it is necessary to compare the formula $(\Delta_m = Ge_{6/12} P_{8/12})$ with the cluster formula $(TCC_{n(bas)} = Zn_{12/12} Ge_{6/6} P_{16/8})$ from (47): when comparing, it can be seen that $(r = 1/6) > (t = 1/12)$. Therefore, the formula $\{\Delta_m = Ge_{6/12} P_{8/12}\}$ from the formula $(TCC_{n(bas)} = Zn_{12/12} Ge_{6/6} P_{16/8})$ can be subtracted only once. In this case $(k = 1)$ and $\{n(bas) = 2\}$. Then we get the formula $TCC_{n=1}$ according to (40):

$$(TCC_{n=1} = A_{tbc} B_{(r-k)t} C_{(t+r-k)t} = Zn_{12/12} Ge_{6/12} P_{16/12} \equiv Zn_6 Ge_3 P_8) \dots (49)$$

The CC branch of the m -group of HS, to which $ZnGeP_2$ belongs, can be represented as follows:

$$\text{The branch of the CC } m\text{-group is } A_{tbc} B_{\{r-k-t+(n-1)t\}ac} C_{\{r-k-t+nt\}ab} \equiv Zn_{12t} Ge_{3(n-t+r-t)k} P_{8((n-t+r-t)k)} \equiv Zn_{12/12} Ge_{(3n+3-3k)/12} P_{(8n+16-8k)/12} \equiv Zn_6 Ge_{3n-(n+1)} \dots (50)$$

Since the compound experimentally obtained in [25] $(TCC_{n=2} = ZnGeP_2)$ in the desired HS m -group turned out to be the second member, given the continuity of the HS cluster $(Zn_6 Ge_3 P_8 = TCC_{n=1})$ must exist. As can be seen, the relative germanium content in the cluster $(TCC_{n=1} = Zn_6 Ge_3 P_8)$ is less than in the cluster $(TCC_{n=2} = ZnGeP_2)$, which in the synthesis of $Zn_6 Ge_3 P_8$ can give some advantages over $ZnGeP_2$ while preserving the basic nonlinear optical characteristics of the material.

According to (19), the formula of the first homologue $(TCC_{n=1} = p. 2 = A_{bc} B_{ac} C_{2ab} = Zn_{12} Ge_6 P_{16})$ in am -HS and the formula $(TCC_{n=1} = A_{tbc} B_{(r-k)t} C_{(t+r-k)t} = Zn_{12/12} Ge_{6/12} P_{16/12} \equiv Zn_{12} Ge_6 P_{16} \equiv Zn_6 Ge_3 P_8)$ coincide, which indicates that formula (50) belongs to the CC branch of the am -HS, and the base cluster $(ZnGeP_2 = TCC_{n(bas)=2})$ belongs to the am -HS.

Comparison of experiments (known from the literature) with the results of the calculation of HS

The operability of the method of calculating the HS of chemical compounds presented here and in [4]-[7] is confirmed by numerous experiments taken from the literature [10]: so, if in formula (25), $A_{bc} B_{nac} C_{(n+1)ab}$, replace $A^{a+} \equiv Li^+, Na^+, K^+, Rb^+$, etc., $B^{b+} \equiv Ti^{4+}$, $C^{c-} \equiv O^{2-}$, then for the systems $(Na^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$ and $(Li^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$, the following can be obtained:

1) Thirteen experimentally obtained compounds of the system $(Na^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$: $n = 1$ [21-23,26], 2 [21-23,26], 3 [21,22], 4 [21,22,27], 5 [21,22], 6 [22,27-29], 7 [30], 8 [31], 9 [30], 12 [27-29,32,], 14 [30], 16 [30], 18 [33,34].

2) Seven compounds of the system $(Li^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$ obey the calculated formula (22) (direction of development of $HS - TiO_2 - Li_4 Ti^{4+}_n O_{2(n+1)}$; $n = 1$ [24,35,36], 2 [35], 3 [36], 4 [37], 5 [36-38], 6 [36,39], 7 [37], 8 [30,36,37], 12 [36]. Based on the calculations of the systems $(Li^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$ and $(Na^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$, formula (22) can be written for the system $(M^+ - Ti^{4+} - O^{2-})$, where $M^+ \equiv Li^+, Na^+, K^+, Rb^+$, so:

The formula (51) obtained here completely coincides with the formula obtained in [22] only on the basis of experiment.

3) When replacing $A^{a+} \equiv K^+$, $B^{b+} \equiv V^{5+}$ and $C^{c-} \equiv O^{2-}$ five compounds of the system $(K^+ - V^{5+} - O^{2-})$ obey the calculated formula (22) (direction of development of $HS - V_2 O_5$): $K_{10} V^{5+}_{2n} O_{5(n+1)}$; $n = 3, 5, 15, 20, 25$ [38,40,41];

4) When replacing $A^{a+} \equiv Ba^{2+}$, $B^{b+} \equiv Cu^{2+}$ and $C^{c-} \equiv O^{2-}$ five compounds of the system $(Ba^{2+} - Cu^{2+} - O^{2-})$ obey the calculated formula (22) (direction of development of $HS - CuO - BaCu^{2+}_n O_{n+1}$; $n = 1$ [12, 42-44], $n = 2$ [44]; $n = 3, 7$ [45]; $n = 4$ [12];

5) When replacing $A^{a+} \equiv Ba^{2+}$, $B^{b+} \equiv Cu^{2+}$ and $C^{c-} \equiv O^{2-}$ three compounds of the system $(Ba^{2+} - Cu^{2+} - O^{2-})$ obey the calculated formula (17) (direction of development of $HS - BaO - Ba_n Cu^{2+}_{on+1}$; $n = 1$ [12, 42,43], $n = 2$ [14, 45], $n = 3$ [44].

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